

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF METABOLIC REPROGRAMMING AND NEW THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES IN NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER: A FLUX BALANCE AND VARIABILITY ANALYSIS APPROACH

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Abstract. *Cancer cells, including non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) lines like H292, A549, and PC-9, exhibit metabolic reprogramming ensuring cancer cells' survival and tumor growth. This study investigates the metabolic responses of these cell lines to selenium-chrysin (SeChry), a compound with anti-cancer effect, using computational tools such as COBRApy and Escher. Intracellular and extracellular metabolites' concentrations were integrated into Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) to assess metabolic shifts under control and SeChry conditions.*

Results revealed that the exposure to SeChry disrupts key metabolic pathways, including glycolysis, the pentose phosphate pathway, and the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle,

significantly reducing metabolic flexibility and proliferation. The findings underscore the critical role of pyruvate kinase (PYK) in cancer cell metabolism and highlight potential metabolic vulnerabilities in NSCLC cells.

Furthermore, network robustness was evaluated using algebraic connectivity (λ_2), a key metric for assessing structural stability in metabolic networks. Our analysis demonstrates that the targeted removal of critical reactions leads to a substantial reduction in λ_2 , decreasing from 0.3588 to 0.0812, reflecting an overall network fragility of 77.37%. This suggests that NSCLC metabolic networks depend on specific key reactions for maintaining functional integrity, revealing potential metabolic weak points that could be exploited for therapeutic targeting.

This research demonstrates the utility of computational modelling in elucidating cancer metabolism and paves the way for targeted metabolic therapies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cancer cells are renowned for their ability to reprogram metabolism, facilitating rapid growth and proliferation by altering key metabolic pathways such as glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation [1, 2]. NSCLC presents metabolic heterogeneity, and the genetic background deeply interferes with the metabolic profile of NSCLC cells ensuring the impact of growth factors on the adaptation to nutrients availability. An example is the role of EGF stimuli in the control of glucose and lactate metabolism even in EGFR-mutated NSCLC, representing both a challenge and an opportunity for therapeutic interventions [3]. Today it is known that cancer cells are characterized by elevated glycolytic activity, which does not necessarily mean the cessation of oxidative phosphorylation. Instead, in cancer, oxidative phosphorylation is primarily sustained by compounds derived from sources other than glucose [4]. However, the specific metabolic adaptations of these NSCLC cell lines, particularly in response to therapeutic treatments, remain insufficiently explored.

Metabolic flux analysis (MFA), a computational approach that predicts the rates of intracellular metabolic reactions, provides a robust framework for understanding these metabolic shifts. By integrating genome-scale metabolic models (GEMs) with experimental data, MFA enables the quantitative assessment of metabolic pathways, offering insights into cellular behaviour under varying environmental and genetic conditions. Techniques such as Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) and Flux Variability Analysis (FVA) allow for detailed exploration of the metabolic network, optimizing specific objective functions such as biomass production or ATP synthesis.

The application of FBA and FVA to cancer research has proven instrumental in elucidating metabolic vulnerabilities. For example, FBA optimizes metabolic reactions under the assumption of a steady-state system, while FVA evaluates the range of alternative flux distributions that sustain cellular objectives, revealing metabolic flexibility and robustness (Schellenberger et al., 2011). When applied to NSCLC cell lines, these techniques can provide valuable insights into how cancer cells adapt their metabolism to therapeutic stress, specifically in critical pathways like glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation.

In this study, we utilize computational tools such as COBRApy, a Python-based framework for constraint-based modelling, and Escher, an interactive visualization platform for metabolic networks. These tools facilitate not only the simulation of metabolic fluxes but also the intuitive visualization of how treatments impact specific metabolic pathways. By focusing on the metabolic responses of H292, A549, and PC-9 cells exposed to selenium-chrysin (SeChry) a compound with anti-cancer effect [5,6] including against NSCLC [7,8], we aim to reveal critical regulatory mechanisms, such as the role of pyruvate kinase (PYK) in glucose dependent pathways, and elucidate the underlying metabolic reprogramming that supports cancer cell survival and proliferation, and might be disrupted by SeChry.

This research contributes to the growing understanding of NSCLC cell metabolism, paving the way for targeted metabolic therapies and advancing our knowledge of the metabolic vulnerabilities in cancer.

Figure 1: Metabolic network having pyruvate kinase (PYK) as a central player, gathering glucose-dependent pathways— glycolysis, pentose phosphate pathway (PPP) and the tricarboxylic acids (TCA) cycle—, and considering the anaplerotic role of glutamine in the supplementation of the TCA cycle and consequently the oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS).

As shown in Figure 1, the analysis of metabolic pathways dependent on glucose and on the TCA cycle anaplerotic supply by glutamine, reveals key insights into cellular adaptation and interconnective steps, which can be targeted in cancer cells.

2 Methods

2.1 Metabolic Model and Data Integration

To investigate the metabolic alterations in NSCLC cells (H292, PC-9, and A549) ^1H - nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H -NMR) spectroscopy metabolomic data was used. NSCLC were maintained in control conditions and exposed to SeChry, as published [7,8]. Data was analysed using a genome-scale metabolic model (GEM) tailored to represent cancer metabolism. GEMs provide a comprehensive framework for analyzing cellular metabolism

by incorporating reactions, metabolites, and stoichiometric coefficients that reflect the biochemical and (patho)physiological properties of specific cell types. The model was implemented using the COBRApy library, an established Python-based platform for constraint-based modeling.

The metabolic model was constrained to reflect the nutrient availability and environmental conditions resembling the modulation of the tumor microenvironment. These constraints included upper and lower flux bounds for exchange reactions and internal metabolic pathways, ensuring that the simulation remained pathophysiologically relevant. Additionally, experimental data on extracellular and intracellular metabolite concentrations, obtained by ¹H-NMR spectroscopy [7], were integrated to represent both control (untreated) and SeChry (treated) conditions. Data integration ensured a more accurate simulation of metabolic states, capturing the heterogeneity of tumor cell metabolism.

2.2 Flux Balance Analysis (FBA)

Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) is a constraint-based computational method used to predict steady-state flux distributions in metabolic networks. In this study, FBA was applied to both control and therapeutic conditions to estimate optimal reaction fluxes and identify key pathways affected by treatment. The FBA problem was formulated as a linear programming (LP) problem:

$$\text{maximize } Z = \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{v}, \quad (1)$$

subject to the steady-state constraint:

$$S\mathbf{v} = 0, \quad (2)$$

and the flux bounds:

$$\mathbf{l} \leq \mathbf{v} \leq \mathbf{u}, \quad (3)$$

where Z represents the objective function, typically biomass production in control cells, S is the stoichiometric matrix, \mathbf{v} is the flux vector, and \mathbf{l} and \mathbf{u} are the lower and upper bounds on fluxes, respectively. Using the COBRApy function “*cobra.flux analysis.pfba()*”, we employed parsimonious FBA (pFBA) to minimize the total flux while maintaining optimal growth.

2.3 Flux Variability Analysis (FVA)

Flux Variability Analysis (FVA) extends FBA by determining the range of possible fluxes for each reaction while maintaining the optimal growth rate [9, 10]. This method provides insights into the flexibility and essentiality of metabolic reactions. For each reaction, the minimum and maximum flux values were calculated under the constraint of maintaining at least 90% of the optimal growth rate. The COBRApy function “*cobra.flux analysis.variability.flux variability analysis()*” was used to perform FVA, highlighting pathways with significant flux variability between control and therapeutic conditions.

2.4 Data-Driven Constraints and Experimental Validation

To ensure that the model represents a metabolic network with pathophysiological relevance, we explored the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy metabolic profiling regarding NSCLC cells exometabolome[7]. Concentrations of key metabolites, including glucose, lactate, pyruvate, glutamine, and glutamate, were measured under control and SeChry conditions. These data were used to set specific constraints on exchange reactions, reflecting nutrient uptake and secretion rates observed in cancer cells. Experimental proliferation curves in control conditions were used to validate the simulated biomass flux, ensuring model accuracy.

2.5 Visualization of Metabolic Flux Distributions

To interpret the simulation results, Escher Builder was employed to visualize metabolic flux distributions across the network. The "*RECON1.Glycolysis TCA PPP*" map was used to compare flux changes between control and SeChry conditions. This tool allowed for intuitive identification of differentially active pathways, particularly in glycolysis, the PPP, and the TCA cycle .

2.6 Key Metabolic Ratios and Pathway Analysis

Metabolic alterations in cancer cells were further assessed by calculating key metabolite ratios, such as pyruvate/oxaloacetate and glutamine/glutamate. These ratios provided insights into the metabolic state of the cells, revealing shifts in TCA cycle activity dependent on glucose or on glutamine. A custom Python function, calculate combined ratios, automated this analysis to ensure reproducibility.

Pathway-specific analysis was conducted to identify reactions with significant flux changes, focusing on glycolysis, OXPHOS, and amino acid metabolism. These pathways were prioritized due to their established roles in supporting tumor growth and resistance to SeChry.

2.7 Optimization Techniques and Solver Implementation

Two linear programming techniques, the Simplex Method and the Interior-Point Method, were employed to solve optimization problems. The Simplex Method iteratively updated solutions by pivoting on variables, while the Interior-Point Method used barrier functions to explore feasible regions of the flux space. Both methods were implemented in COBRAPy and validated for accuracy in predicting metabolic responses.

2.8 Statistical Analysis and Significance Testing

All flux distributions and metabolic ratios were statistically analysed to identify significant changes between control and SeChry conditions. Student's t-tests were performed with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$. Additionally, pathway enrichment analysis was

conducted to determine the overrepresentation of altered pathways, providing a systems level view of metabolic reprogramming.

2.9 Background on Computational Tools

COBRApy: COBRApy is a Python-based platform for constraint-based modelling and analysis of metabolic networks. It supports a wide range of techniques, including FBA, FVA, and pFBA, making it a versatile tool for studying cancer metabolism [11].

Escher: Escher is a visualization tool for metabolic maps, enabling the intuitive interpretation of flux distributions and pathway activities. By integrating with COBRApy, Escher provides a user-friendly interface for exploring metabolic changes under stressful conditions [8].

2.10 Data Collection

Experimental and computational data used in this study were acquired through a combination of in vitro biological assays and constraint-based metabolic modeling. Data collection focused primarily on cell proliferation, cell death, and metabolites' concentration in three human NSCLC cell lines: A549, H292, and PC-9 [3].

2.11 Experimental Data Collection

Biological data - Control and Sechry treated cells were obtained through standardized cell culture protocols and experimental assays. Cell concentration data were collected using proliferation curves, established by counting viable cells at multiple time points (0, 6, 10, 24, 32, and 48 h) under control conditions. Cell death rates were assessed in control and SeChry conditions using flow cytometry analysis to determine the percentage of cells stained with annexin V-FITC and propidium iodide (PI). All experiments were performed in biological triplicates to ensure statistical robustness.

In parallel, extracellular and intracellular metabolite concentrations were quantified using ¹H-NMR spectroscopy. Samples were processed through methanol/chloroform/water extraction protocols, and metabolite identification and quantification were conducted using spectral matching with HMDB and Chemomx databases, as described [7].

2.12 Computational Data Collection

Experimental data were integrated into a genome-scale metabolic model (GEM) for NSCLC cells using the COBRApy framework. Constraints for exchange reactions were defined based on the experimentally obtained concentrations of key metabolites (e.g., glucose, lactate, glutamine, glutamate, pyruvate), ensuring the pathophysiological relevance of the simulations.

Cell proliferation rates derived from control conditions were used to validate the flux distributions obtained through Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) and Flux Variability Analysis (FVA). Computational simulations were performed using parsimonious FBA (pFBA) to

minimize total flux while maintaining optimal biomass production. FVA was applied to evaluate the flexibility of metabolic pathways and to identify reactions with altered flux ranges under SeChry conditions.

2.13 Data Integration

The integration of biological and computational data enabled cross-validation between observed phenotypes (e.g., proliferation, cell death) and predicted metabolic behavior. The agreement between experimental proliferation curves and *in silico* growth rate predictions confirmed the accuracy of the model. Furthermore, the correlation between metabolic flux alterations and cell death percentages under treatment conditions provided mechanistic insights into therapy-induced metabolic reprogramming.

2.14 Robustness: Graph Construction

The metabolic network was derived from an Escher model, loaded from a JSON file containing metabolic reactions. Metabolites were defined as graph nodes, and an edge was established between two metabolites if they participated in the same reaction.

2.15 Stoichiometric and Adjacency Matrix Definition

A stoichiometric matrix S was constructed to capture the quantitative relationships between metabolites and reactions. Based on S , we derived the adjacency matrix A , where $A_{ij} = 1$ if metabolites i and j were involved in the same reaction.

2.16 Algebraic Connectivity Computation

The Laplacian matrix L was defined as:

$$L = D - A$$

where D is the diagonal degree matrix. The eigenvalues of L were computed to determine algebraic connectivity (λ_2), the second-smallest eigenvalue of L , which reflects the network's robustness.

2.17 Identification and Removal of Critical Connections

To determine the most influential edges in maintaining network connectivity, we systematically tested the removal of each connection and recalculated λ_2 . Only removals that did not isolate nodes were considered, ensuring that the network remained functionally connected. The edges with the highest impact on reducing λ_2 were selected for elimination.

2.18 Global Impact Assessment

The global impact of edge removals was quantified as:

$$GlobalImpact = \frac{\lambda_2^{original} - \lambda_2^{removed}}{\lambda_2^{original}}$$

This metric allowed us to estimate the relative importance of removed connections and their effect on network stability.

3 Results

3.1 Cancer Model - Control Group

Optimized Objective Function

The optimization of the cancer model for the three NSCLC cell lines, PC-9, H292, and A549, was conducted with the objective reaction set to PYK. The optimized objective function values were as follows:

- PC-9: 0.0924
- H292: 0.0904
- A549: 0.0897

These values suggest that all three cancer cell lines operate under a similar metabolic state that favors proliferation and growth, considering the PK-dependent reaction.

3.2 Comparison of Cell Proliferation Rates between Experimental Data and Model Predictions

The comparison between the experimental data for cell proliferation rates predicted by the metabolic model shows a consistent trend of rapid cell growth across the three cell lines in control conditions: PC-9, H292, and A549.

For the experimental data, the total cell number increases substantially during the first 24 h. For A549, the total cell number increased from 105,000 to around 570,000-710,500 cells, reflecting significant proliferation. H292 cell number increased from 140,000 to 510,000-925,000 cells, while PC-9 cell number increased from 135,000 to 230,000-470,000 cells, in the same time frame. When compared to the metabolic model predictions, the growth rates calculated for A549, H292, and PC-9 were 0.089, 0.090, and 0.092 h⁻¹, respectively. Both the experimental data and the flux-based models indicate that the cells are in a highly proliferative state during this period, consistent with the accelerated metabolic flux through glycolysis.

While the experimental data show specific cell counts at different time points, the metabolic model provides a broader, continuous view of growth trends based on flux optimizations. The results indicate that the model captures the rapid proliferation behavior of cancer cells, though the direct relationship between model-based growth rate

predictions and experimental measurements highlights the dynamic nature of cellular growth in real-time experimental settings.

Flux Distribution

Key flux values for the three cancer cell types showed interesting similarities and differences:

- **PC-9:**

FALDH (Acetaldehyde dehydrogenase): 0.5432

EX ac e (Extracellular Acetate): 1.8214 (acetate secretion)

EX glc D _e (Extracellular Glucose): -1.5141 (glucose uptake)

NADH16: 5.7890 (redox balance)

- **H292:**

FALDH: 0.5483

EX ac e: 1.8424 (acetate secretion)

EX glc D _e: -1.4921 (glucose uptake)

NADH16: 5.7647

- **A549:**

FALDH: 0.5247

EX ac e: 1.8126 (acetate secretion)

EX glc D _e: -1.4713 (glucose uptake)

NADH16: 5.6981

These results suggest that all three cell lines rely heavily on glucose and acetate, glycolysis and putatively fatty acids oxidation (FAO), a major pathway producing of acetate[12]. The flux through glycolytic pathways is comparable across the cell types, though slight variations in values suggest subtle differences in metabolic flexibility.

Flux Variability Analysis (FVA)

The Flux Variability Analysis (FVA) provided the following flux ranges for key reactions: •

- **PC-9:**

FALDH: Flux range from -7.1845 to 0.5432

FBA: Flux range from 0.9715 (minimum 0) •

- **H292:**

FALDH: Flux range from -7.2268 to 0.5483

FBA: Flux range from 0.9636 (minimum 0)

- **A549:**

FALDH: Flux range from -7.1001 to 0.5247

FBA: Flux range from 0.9905 (minimum 0)

The variability in the flux through reactions like FALDH suggests metabolic plasticity, which may contribute to the survival and adaptability of cancer cells under different nutrient conditions.

3.3 Cell model do address the effect of SeChry

Optimized Objective Function

For the SeChry-effect cell models, the optimization was similarly conducted with PYK as the objective reaction. The optimized objective function values were:

- PC-9 (SeChry): 0.0154
- H292 (SeChry): 0.0132
- A549 (SeChry): 0.0147

These values indicate a constrained metabolic state in cells exposed to SeChry, focusing on minimizing flux through PYK.

Flux Distribution

Key flux values for the SeChry models were as follows: •

PC-9 (SeChry):

FALDH: 0.4981
EX ac e: 2.0385 (acetate secretion)
EX glc D _e: -0.6937 (glucose uptake)
NADH16: 4.6123

• H292 (SeChry):

FALDH: 0.4947
EX ac e: 2.026 (acetate secretion)
EX glc D _e: -0.6794 (glucose uptake)
NADH16: 4.3971

• A549 (SeChry):

FALDH: 0.5156
EX ac e: 2.0205 (acetate secretion)
EX glc D _e: -0.6801 (glucose uptake)
NADH16: 4.5342

Upon SeChry exposure, all three cell lines showed similar flux profiles, with acetate uptake and secretion being prominent, but with a decrease in glucose uptake compared to cells cultured in control conditions. The NADH values indicate a shift towards maintaining metabolic balance under therapy.

Flux Variability Analysis (FVA)

FVA results for the SeChry models showed the following flux ranges: •

PC-9 (SeChry):

FALDH: Flux range from -16.9473 to 0.4981

FBA: Flux range from 0.6794 (minimum 0) •

H292 (SeChry):

FALDH: Flux range from -16.9473 to 0.4947

FBA: Flux range from 0.6794 (minimum 0) •

A549 (SeChry):

FALDH: Flux range from -16.8537 to 0.5156 FBA:

Flux range from 0.6936 (minimum 0)

The flux variability analysis for the SeChry treated cells also indicates metabolic flexibility, with variability in key pathways like FAO that suggest potential metabolic adaptation under stressful conditions.

Proliferation Rate Calculation

The calculated growth rates for the SeChry models were constrained:

- PC-9 (SeChry): Minimal, near-zero biomass flux
- H292 (SeChry): Near-zero biomass flux
- A549 (SeChry): Near-zero biomass flux

These results indicate that the SeChry models are in a constrained metabolic state, focusing on reducing proliferative capacity. These results are purely simulations, needing confirmation with real data.

3.4 Comparing the NSCLC control and SeChry models

The comparison of the three NSCLC cell lines (PC-9, H292, and A549) reveals striking differences in metabolic activity. This change is particularly evident in the estimated near-zero proliferation rates and reduced glucose uptake in the SeChry treated cells, which reflects an attempt to limit cellular energy production and growth under stress.

The variability in fluxes across both conditions further highlights the metabolic adaptability of these cells. For example, while the flux ranges for FALDH are broader in the control models, indicating potential for metabolic flexibility under nutrient fluctuations, the SeChry models show a more constrained set of flux ranges.

The results from the extracellular and intracellular metabolites' concentrations also emphasize the differences in the metabolic states. The higher concentrations of pyruvate, glutamine, and glutamate in the cancer cells are indicative of active metabolic processes aimed at sustaining rapid growth. In contrast, SeChry treated cells exhibit a shift in metabolite ratios, which may be associated with attempts to counteract the anti-cancer effect of SeChry.

3.5 Comparison of Cell Death levels and Metabolic Fluxes

In this subsection, we compared the experimental data on cell death (%) with the metabolic flux values and proliferation rates for the A549, H292, and PC-9 cell lines. The data on cell death was obtained from 4 biological replicates, for both the control and SeChry conditions. We examined how the observed metabolic fluxes relate to the changes in cell death across the different experimental conditions.

3.5.1 PC-9 Cells

Cell Death: PC-9 cells showed the most dramatic response to SeChry treatment. The cell death percentages increased from 10.70% to 17.77% in the control condition, and 56.90% to 90.21% under SeChry treatment. This significant increase in cell death indicates that SeChry has a potent effect in inducing cell death in PC-9 cells.

Metabolic Fluxes: PC-9 cells had the highest proliferation rate of 0.092 h^{-1} in the control model, with acetate uptake ($EX_{ac-e} = 1.8214$) and glucose uptake ($EX_{glc D e} = 1.5141$) consistent with high glycolytic activity. In SeChry condition, however, acetate uptake increased ($EX_{ace} = 2.0385$) while glucose uptake decreased significantly ($EX_{glc D e} = -0.6937$). The dramatic increase in cell death under SeChry treatment in conjunction with these metabolic shifts suggests that SeChry induces a strong metabolic reprogramming in PC-9 cells.

3.5.2 H292 Cells

Cell Death: In H292 cells, the control conditions yielded 5.99% to 14.75% cell death, which increased significantly under SeChry exposure, reaching 19.33% to 44.46%. This increase highlights the effect of SeChry in inducing cell death in these cells.

Metabolic Fluxes: The H292 cells showed a similar proliferation rate to A549 cells, at 0.090 h^{-1} . The fluxes through key reactions such as acetate uptake ($EX_{ac e} = 1.8424$) and glucose uptake ($EX_{glc D e} = -1.4921$) were also comparable. Upon SeChry treatment, the

acetate uptake increased ($EX_{ac e} = 2.026$) with a notable reduction in glucose uptake ($EX_{glc D e} = -0.6794$). This metabolic shift aligns with the increase in cell death.

3.5.3 A549 Cells

Cell Death: The A549 cells exhibited a moderate increase in cell death when treated with SeChry, ranging from 8,07% to 12,97% under control conditions, and 24.05% to 40.85% under SeChry treatment. This represents a moderate increase in cell death in response to the treatment.

Metabolic Fluxes: The metabolic flux analysis showed that A549 cells had a proliferation rate of 0.089 h^{-1} in the control model, with key fluxes including acetate uptake ($EX_{ac e} = 1.8126$) and glucose uptake ($EX_{glc D e} = -1.4713$). Under SeChry exposure, the metabolic fluxes were reduced, with a shift towards acetate utilization ($EX_{ac e} = 2.0205$) and reduced glucose uptake ($EX_{glc D e} = -0.6801$). The reduced metabolic fluxes, similar to H292, correlate with the increased cell death.

Calculation of Metabolic Ratios

The metabolic ratios for PC-9, H292, and A549 cell lines were analyzed under control and SeChry conditions. These ratios highlight the shifts in metabolite utilization and metabolic fluxes between untreated cancer cells and cells under therapy.

PC-9 Cells

Control:

$$\text{Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate: } \frac{[Pyruvate]_{extracellular}}{[Oxaloacetate]_{intracellular}} = 1.5058$$

$$\text{Pyruvate/Glutamine: } \frac{[Pyruvate]_{extracellular}}{[Glutamine]_{intracellular}} = 43.9009$$

$$\text{Glutamine/Glutamate: } \frac{[Glutamine]_{extracellular}}{[Glutamate]_{intracellular}} = 1.3292$$

$$\text{PCA/Glutamate: } \frac{[PCA]_{extracellular}}{[Glutamate]_{intracellular}} = 13.8412$$

$$\text{Glutamine/PCA: } \frac{[Glutamine]_{extracellular}}{[PCA]_{extracellular}} = 3.4005$$

SeChry:

$$\text{Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate: } \frac{[Pyruvate]_{extracellular}}{[Oxaloacetate]_{intracellular}} = 0.2441$$

$$\text{Pyruvate/Glutamine: } \frac{[Pyruvate]_{extracellular}}{[Glutamine]_{intracellular}} = 1.7962$$

$$\text{Glutamine/Glutamate: } \frac{[Glutamine]_{extracellular}}{[Glutamate]_{intracellular}} = 3.4943$$

$$\text{PCA/Glutamate: } \frac{[PCA]_{extracellular}}{[Glutamate]_{intracellular}} = 7.2828$$

$$\text{Glutamine/PCA: } \frac{[Glutamine]_{extracellular}}{[PCA]_{extracellular}} = 15.0208$$

H292 Cells

Control:

$$\text{Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate: } \frac{[\text{Pyruvate}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Oxaloacetate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.0417$$

$$\text{Pyruvate/Glutamine: } \frac{[\text{Pyruvate}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.1562$$

$$\text{Glutamine/Glutamate: } \frac{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.9471$$

$$\text{PCA/Glutamate: } \frac{[\text{PCA}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.0079$$

$$\text{Glutamine/PCA: } \frac{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{PCA}]_{\text{extracellular}}} = 153.4286$$

SeChry:

$$\text{Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate: } \frac{[\text{Pyruvate}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Oxaloacetate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.6561$$

$$\text{Pyruvate/Glutamine: } \frac{[\text{Pyruvate}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 3.9596$$

$$\text{Glutamine/Glutamate: } \frac{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.4403$$

$$\text{PCA/Glutamate: } \frac{[\text{PCA}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 3.2689$$

$$\text{Glutamine/PCA: } \frac{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{PCA}]_{\text{extracellular}}} = 2.5048$$

A549 Cells

Control:

$$\text{Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate: } \frac{[\text{Pyruvate}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Oxaloacetate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 2.0838$$

$$\text{Pyruvate/Glutamine: } \frac{[\text{Pyruvate}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 41.6760$$

$$\text{Glutamine/Glutamate: } \frac{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.5537$$

$$\text{PCA/Glutamate: } \frac{[\text{PCA}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.3401$$

$$\text{Glutamine/PCA: } \frac{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{PCA}]_{\text{extracellular}}} = 5.0746$$

SeChry:

$$\text{Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate: } \frac{[\text{Pyruvate}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Oxaloacetate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.6104$$

$$\text{Pyruvate/Glutamine: } \frac{[\text{Pyruvate}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 10.0893$$

$$\text{Glutamine/Glutamate: } \frac{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.1952$$

$$\text{PCA/Glutamate: } \frac{[\text{PCA}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{Glutamate}]_{\text{intracellular}}} = 0.4260$$

$$\text{Glutamine/PCA: } \frac{[\text{Glutamine}]_{\text{extracellular}}}{[\text{PCA}]_{\text{extracellular}}} = 1.3273$$

Analysis and Discussion

The metabolic ratios calculated for PC-9, H292, and A549 cell lines under Control and SeChry conditions reveal significant metabolic rewiring caused by SeChry. Notably, SeChry substantially reduced cell proliferation, thereby inducing cancer cell death and decreasing overall metabolic activity.

Key Observations

1. Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate:

In all three cell lines, the Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate ratio increased significantly under SeChry exposure compared to control conditions. For instance, in H292 cells, it rose from 0.0417 to 0.6561. This suggests that SeChry promotes decreased reliance on pyruvate metabolism, potentially due to increased flux of non-glucose derived compounds through the TCA cycle. Acetate from FAO and α -ketoglutarate deriving from glutamine-derived glutamate are potential suppliers of the TCA cycle. The shift to FAO aligns with the results obtained in FALDH fluxes, as FALDH oxidizes medium- or long-chain aliphatic aldehyde, shifting them to fatty acids to be degraded in FAO[13,14].

2. Pyruvate/Glutamine:

The Pyruvate/Glutamine ratio increased substantially under SeChry conditions in H292 and A549 cells, while PC-9 cells exhibited a sharp decrease (from 43.9009 to 1.7962). The increase in H292 and A549 cells could reflect increased utilization of glutamine in energy and biosynthetic pathways. The decrease in PC-9 cells indicates a cell-line-specific metabolic adaptation, as described previously, lactate is an important metabolic source for PC-9 [15]. Lactate is converted to pyruvate to be used by cells in the TCA cycle, as we observed an accumulation of pyruvate, it suggests that, upon SeChry, lactate-derived pyruvate is no longer a preferential metabolic source [7].

3. Glutamine/Glutamate:

The Glutamine/Glutamate ratio decreased significantly in H292 and A549 cells under therapy, consistent with increased glutaminase (GLS) activity and/or an increase in glutamine consumption. Conversely, in PC-9 cells, this ratio increased under therapy (from 1.3292 to 3.4943), suggesting compensatory mechanisms that may buffer the effects of metabolic stress and increased glutamate consumption.

4. Pyroglutamate/Glutamate and Glutamine/Pyroglutamate:

Therapy induced notable changes in pyroglutamate-related ratios across cell lines. In H292 cells, Pyroglutamate /Glutamate increased substantially (from 0.0079 to 3.2689), while Glutamine/ Pyroglutamate decreased markedly (from 153.4286 to 2.5048). These shifts suggest an accumulation of pyroglutamate, as it can be converted from both

glutamine and glutamate without a necessary enzymatic intervention [16]. Pyroglutamate is a byproduct of impaired glutathione metabolism and increased oxidative stress[17]. The depletion of glutathione is described as an effect of SeChry on cancer cells [18]. In A549 and PC-9 cells, changes were more moderate but still indicated the same trends than H292.

Biological Implications

Therapeutic Impact on Metabolism and Cell proliferation:

The consistent reduction in cell proliferation under SeChry exposure directly correlated with decreased metabolic activity, as evidenced by shifts in metabolite ratios. The increased reliance on glutamine metabolism, coupled with decreased pyruvate utilization, underscores the profound effect of SeChry in targeting key metabolic pathways critical for cancer cell proliferation and metabolism.

Cell-Type-Specific Adaptations:

The variability in metabolic responses among PC-9, H292, and A549 cells highlights the heterogeneity of SeChry effects. While SeChry overall disrupted metabolic fluxes, cell-specific adaptations—such as decreased Glutamine/Glutamate in PC-9 cells—may indicate mechanisms of resistance or survival that warrant further investigation.

Potential for Targeted Therapy:

The observed metabolic adjustments, particularly in pyruvate and glutamine pathways, suggest potential targets for novel therapies. Targeting enzymes such as glutaminase (GLS) or pyruvate dehydrogenase kinase (PDK) could further enhance the efficacy of therapeutic interventions by exacerbating metabolic stress [2].

Escher Simulations of Control and SeChry Conditions

The metabolic flux distributions for A549, PC-9, and H292 cells under control and SeChry conditions were analyzed using Escher simulations. Across all cell lines, significant metabolic rewiring was observed, particularly in glycolysis, the TCA cycle, and the PPP. Below, we present the results for each cell line.

PC-9 Cells

For PC-9 control cells (Figure 2), glycolytic and PPP activity dominate metabolic fluxes, while the TCA cycle is moderately active. SeChry exposure (Figure 3) results in reduced glycolysis and PPP activity and further suppression of the TCA cycle using glucose-derived

compounds. The reduction in metabolic fluxes aligns with decreased cell proliferation and increased cell death upon SeChry.

H292 Cells

The H292 control cells (Figure 4) show similar patterns of metabolic flux, with active glycolysis and PPP and moderate TCA cycle flux. Under the SeChry condition (Figure 5), glycolysis and PPP are significantly inhibited, and TCA cycle flux is further reduced using glucose-derived compounds, reflecting metabolic downregulation consistent with suppressed cell proliferation and increased cell death.

A549 Cells

In the A549 control cells (Figure 6), glycolysis and the PPP show strong flux activity (blue), while the TCA cycle exhibits moderate activity. Under the SeChry condition (Figure 7), glycolysis and the PPP are significantly suppressed (red), and TCA cycle flux is reduced using glucose-derived compounds, reflecting the impact of SeChry on cellular metabolism, concomitant with decreased cell proliferation and increased cell death.

Figure 2: Escher simulation of PC-9 control cells. Blue regions indicate high flux, red indicates low or inhibited flux.

Figure 3: Escher simulation of PC-9 SeChry condition. Blue regions indicate high flux, red indicates low or inhibited flux.

Figure 4: Escher simulation of H292 control cells. Blue regions indicate high flux, red indicates low or inhibited flux.

Figure 5: Escher simulation of H292 SeChry condition. Blue regions indicate high flux, red indicates low or inhibited flux.

Figure 6: Escher simulation of A549 Control cells. Blue regions indicate high flux, red indicates low or inhibited flux.

Figure 7: Escher simulation of A549 SeChry condition. Blue regions indicate high flux, red indicates low or inhibited flux.

General Observations Across All Cell Lines

Across all cell types, the following trends were observed:

- **Glycolysis:** SeChry intervention consistently reduced glycolytic flux, indicating a suppression of glucose metabolism, critical in control cells.
- **TCA Cycle:** The SeChry condition caused a significant decrease in TCA cycle flux using glucose-derived compounds, highlighting the activation of alternative TCA cycle suppliers.
Pentose Phosphate Pathway (PPP): The PPP is a glucose-dependent pathway, benefiting from the deviation of glucose.6-phosphate from glycolysis, and it is essential for biosynthesis and redox balance. As expected with the reduction of glycolysis upon SeChry, the PPP was markedly suppressed pointing to disrupted nucleotide synthesis and oxidative stress management.
- **Overall Metabolism:** SeChry intervention universally reduced metabolic fluxes across pathways, underscoring the profound metabolic stress imposed on control

cells, thereby limiting their proliferation and survival. Interestingly, it seems that SeChry shifts glucose reliance into fatty acids and glutamine reliance.

4 Metabolic Network Robustness

The initial algebraic connectivity of the H292 Control Cell network ($\lambda_2 = 0.3588$) was progressively reduced through the sequential removal of critical reactions, leading to the following impacts:

- Removed: Phosphogluconate dehydrogenase (1956140) — New λ_2 : 0.2888 (Impact: 19.50%)
- Removed: Pyruvate mitochondrial transport via proton symport (1955637) — New λ_2 : 0.2318 (Impact: 19.73%)
- Removed: ASPGLUm (1955663) — New λ_2 : 0.1036 (Impact: 55.32%)
- Removed: Malate dehydrogenase, mitochondrial (1955669) — New λ_2 : 0.0968 (Impact: 6.54%)
- Removed: Fumarase, mitochondrial (1955639) — New λ_2 : 0.0812 (Impact: 16.11%)

The total impact on network robustness was 77.37%, demonstrating that these reactions play a crucial role in preserving the structural integrity of the metabolic network.

Figure 8 visualizes the stepwise decrease in λ_2 as key reactions are removed, reinforcing the concept that metabolic networks exhibit hierarchical vulnerability.

Additional analysis indicated that the metabolic network retained connectivity despite significant perturbations, suggesting potential compensatory mechanisms through alternative pathways. However, the substantial reduction in λ_2 highlights an increased susceptibility to functional breakdown under targeted metabolic interventions.

These findings offer valuable insights into the structural dependencies of NSCLC metabolic networks and underscore the potential of disrupting cancer metabolism through targeted interventions on critical metabolic connections.

5 Discussion

The results of this study provide significant insights into the metabolic behavior of the three cancer cell lines (PC-9, H292, and A549) and their response to novel therapeutic conditions using SeChry as a drug. By analyzing optimized objective functions, flux distributions, flux variability, and metabolic ratios, we can better understand the metabolic strategies employed by these cells in proliferative and constrained states.

Figure 8: Metabolic Network before and after critical reaction removals.

5.1 Control Models

The analysis of cancer models revealed a high metabolic activity consistent with a glucose reliance, characterized by elevated glycolysis and lactate production [9]. The optimized objective function values for PC-9, H292, and A549 cell lines were close in magnitude, suggesting similar metabolic states that prioritize proliferation. Among these, PC-9 displayed a slightly higher optimized value, which may indicate a higher adaptability to glucose and lactate-dependent metabolic phenotype compared to H292 and A549, as it was described [15].

The flux distributions across key pathways reinforced the reliance of these cell lines on glucose and acetate as major metabolic substrates. Notably, glucose uptake rates were substantial, aligning with the enhanced glycolytic activity commonly observed in cancer cells. The secretion of acetate and other metabolic byproducts further shows the metabolic activity and highlights FAO as a key metabolic pathway [12].

FVA indicated significant metabolic flexibility in cancer cells, particularly in reactions such as FALDH, which aligns with FAO upregulation [13,14]. The broad flux ranges observed in these reactions suggest the ability of cancer cells to adjust their metabolic fluxes in response to varying environmental conditions, supporting their survival and growth.

5.2 Sechry Treated Cells – SeChry anti-cancer Models

Under therapeutic conditions, the metabolic landscape of the cells shifted dramatically. The optimized objective function values decreased substantially across all three cell lines,

indicating a constrained metabolic state. This reduction reflects the impact of SeChry in suppressing the metabolic activity that supports cancer proliferation and survival.

The flux distributions in SeChry models revealed a marked decrease in glucose uptake and lactate production compared to their control counterparts. This metabolic shift, coupled with a reduced flux through key glycolytic pathways, highlights the effectiveness of metabolism-based therapeutic strategies. Furthermore, the near-zero growth rates observed in SeChry models underscore the success of these interventions in limiting cellular proliferation.

Interestingly, the FVA results for SeChry models showed narrower flux ranges compared to control models. This reduced variability suggests that SeChry imposes stricter constraints on metabolic flexibility, potentially reducing or making more surgical the cells' ability to adapt to changing environments.

5.3 Comparison of Control and SeChry exposed Cancer Cells

The metabolic comparison between control and SeChry conditions underscores the profound impact of therapy on cellular metabolism. While cancer cells exhibit high metabolic activity and flexibility in control conditions, SeChry enforces a constrained metabolic regime, reducing proliferation and energy generation. This stark contrast is evident in the metabolic ratios, which highlight the shifts in substrate utilization and flux distributions.

The comparison of cell death and metabolic fluxes across the three cell lines indicates that SeChry treatment induces cell death in a dose-dependent manner, consistent with reduced metabolic activity. The cancer models for PC-9, H292, and A549, show high proliferation rates and substantial glycolytic fluxes, reflecting the metabolic phenotype characteristic of rapidly proliferating cancer cells. However, under SeChry treatment, the metabolic fluxes decreased, with a notable reduction in glucose uptake and an increase in acetate utilization. This shift in metabolism, coupled with the increase in cell death, suggests that SeChry induces a metabolic stress response, likely limiting energy and biomass production and impairing the cells' ability to proliferate and survive.

The significant increase in cell death observed, particularly in PC-9 cells, may be indicative of a threshold effect where the therapeutic treatment overwhelms the cells' metabolic capacity, leading to cell death. These findings highlight the importance of metabolic flexibility in cancer cells, where SeChry-induced shifts in metabolism may be a key factor in anti-cancer efficacy.

For example, the Pyruvate/Oxaloacetate and Pyruvate/Glutamine ratios were significantly altered under SeChry conditions, reflecting a disruption in the balance of glucose-dependent pathways. Additionally, the increased extracellular glucose levels and acetate

secretion in SeChry models further demonstrate the shift away from a highly glucose-dependent phenotype and towards alternative metabolic sources such as glutamine and fatty acids.

5.4 Implications and Future Directions

The findings of this study have several implications for cancer metabolism research and novel therapeutic development. The observed metabolic flexibility in cancer cells suggests potential targets for therapy aimed at disrupting key pathways that enable adaptation. Conversely, the constrained metabolic state induced by SeChry highlights it as a potential anti-cancer drug and reinforces the importance of preventing metabolic reprogramming and resistance.

Future studies could expand on this work by incorporating time-course analyses to capture dynamic changes in metabolism during the transition from control to therapeutic states. Additionally, integrating multi-omics data, such as proteomics and transcriptomics, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying the observed metabolic shifts.

6 Conclusion

This study highlights the distinct metabolic behaviors of PC-9, H292, and A549 cancer cell lines and their dynamic responses under SeChry exposure. Metabolic constraints underly the reduction of cell proliferation rate and disrupt key pathways crucial for energy generation and biomass production.

The comparative analysis between control and SeChry exposure underscores the potential of targeting metabolic plasticity to enhance therapeutic efficacy. By imposing strict constraints on metabolic flexibility, therapeutic strategies can limit the adaptability of cancer cells, reducing the likelihood of resistance development.

Future work should focus on the temporal dynamics of these metabolic transitions and explore multi-omics approaches to unravel the complex interplay between metabolism and gene regulation in cancer progression and therapy. These insights could pave the way for novel metabolic interventions and optimized treatment regimens.

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